

HEART FAILURE IN PATIENTS WITH COGNITIVE DYSFUNCTION**SH.F.Ubaydullayev**Bukhara State Medical Institute,
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Resume. Heart and brain disorders more frequently co-exist than by chance alone, due to having common risk factors and a degree of interaction. In the setting of heart failure (HF) in the elderly strokes, dementia, and depression are all common and can produce a particularly difficult series of clinical problems to manage. Loss of ability to self-care can lead to very poor quality of life and a dramatic increase in health care expenditure. The Heart Failure Association of the ESC as part of its workshop on physiological monitoring of the complex multi-morbid HF patient reviewed screening, monitoring, prevention, and management of cognitive decline within the setting of HF.(1)

Key words: Heart failure, cognitive impairment, blood pressure, dementia

Heart failure (HF) is a serious health problem in developed countries that affects approximately 2-3% of the adult population with an increasing prevalence of up to 5-15% among people over 60 years of age and up to $\geq 10\%$ among people aged 60-75 years or older.[1] HF is associated with increased mortality and morbidity, frequent hospitalizations and a decrease in quality of life and functional status. (2) An elderly patient with HF is a complex problem for modern healthcare systems, and foremost among the difficulties is the problem of cognitive decline and/or dementia, which make it difficult for the patient to self-care and dramatically increase the cost of providing medical care for HF. As developed countries age, more and more HF is accompanied by these multiple concomitant diseases, many of which often dominate the clinical picture and become the most common cause of hospitalization for HF (3).

Materials and methods. There are many approved questionnaires to identify and, to some extent, assess cognitive impairment. These include the Mini Mental Status Survey (MMSE) and the Montreal Cognitive Test (MoCA). The easiest in the spectrum of cognitive decline syndromes is mild cognitive impairment (MCI). It is advisable to screen for cognitive impairment, as in depression, when a patient (especially elderly) is hospitalized with acute HF. Screening and review should also be carried out regularly in an outpatient setting, although primary care can often detect earlier, milder changes that may be reported by caregivers and family members. MMSE has been used to screen for cognitive impairment, but it is not very sensitive when detecting MCI. MoCA is said to be more sensitive to subtle changes. These screening tools may be useful for differentiating acute

and chronic cognitive decline in HF. Questionnaires reveal a clinical decline in cognitive functions, whereas pathophysiological prerequisites may appear months or years earlier. For example, cerebral atrophy, hyperintensity of white matter, loss of gray matter and asymptomatic cerebral infarcts are frequent imaging findings in patients with HF with and without cognitive dysfunction. Stroke, in particular multiple mini-strokes, is a common cause of disability, cognitive decline and dementia in HF, as in the general population. Strokes are more likely in conditions of HF, since HF is prone to blood hypercoagulation, endothelial dysfunction, inflammatory activation and impaired cerebral autoregulation along with a higher frequency of atrial fibrillation. Heart failure occurs in almost 15% of all strokes, and when they occur, subsequent strokes and death are more likely. Silent strokes are also extremely common in HF and can cause progressive deterioration of cognitive function. Studies show that HF leads to 6.3 for men and 3.6 for women, a greater risk of stroke compared to those who do not have HF. Other comorbidities, including peripheral artery disease, hypertension, ischemia, diabetes, chronic kidney disease and endocrine diseases, may further increase the risk. Dementia can be delayed or prevented if strokes can be prevented or treated very early to limit the loss of brain tissue.

Conclusion. Cognitive decline is a common condition and an independent prognostic marker of adverse outcomes in patients with HF. Assessment of cognitive functions, even with simple screening tests, should be part of a routine clinical examination of patients with HF. Despite the emerging data in clinical practice, CI is still a difficult task for clinicians. Future research involving cognitive function as a relevant endpoint of CH research is warranted. There is a need for a better understanding of the pathogenic links between CN and HF, including molecular, neuroendocrine, epigenetic and psychosocial factors. It is important to identify the relationship between cognitive function and types of HF and concomitant diseases, the use of cardiovascular drugs and devices. In addition, more randomized and controlled trials should be initiated to obtain additional data and implement tools for the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of CN in patients with HF.

References:

- 1.Khasanova, M. T., & Movm-Assistant, K. M. (2021). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT DURING CHRONIC ALCOHOLISM. *Достижения науки и образования*, 80, 81-85.

2. Furqatovich, U. S. (2022). COGNITIVE IMPAIREMENT UNDER THE HEART FAILURE. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 167-171.
3. Khasanova, M. T. (2022). HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN STRUCTURE OF KIDNEY UNDER THE CONSUMPTION OF ENERGY DRINKS IN RATS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 167-171.
4. Хасанова, М. Т., & Убайдуллаев, Ш. Ф. (2022). НАРУШЕНИЕ ПАМЯТИ У БОЛЬНЫХ СЕРДЕЧНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬЮ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 22, 603-607.
5. Khasanova, M. T. (2022). Damage of Energy Drinks on Morphological Structures of Rat's Pancreas. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*. Vol 5 (2022). P. 217, 220.
6. Ilyasov, A. S. (2022). Pathomorphological Changes in Internal Organs Under the Influence of Energy Drinks. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 25, 136-138.
7. Илясов, А. С., Тўйкул, М., & Ҳасанова, Қ. (2022). ЭНЕРГЕТИК ИЧИМЛИКЛАРНИНГ АЁЛЛАР РЕПРОДУКТИВ СИСТЕМАСИГА ТАЪСИРИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(5), 299-303.
8. Khasanova, M. T. (2022). POSTNATAL CONTRACEPTION METHODS BY PROGESTINS. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 2(10), 72-78.
9. Khasanova, M. T. Effects of Energy Drinks on the Cell Structure of Organism.
10. Furqatovich, U. S. (2022). Memory Dysfunction after Sudden Cardiac Arrest. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 1(9), 129-135.
11. Хасанова, М. (2022). ИНФЕКЦИИ МОЧЕВЫВОДЯЩИХ ПУТЕЙ ВО ВРЕМЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(23), 103-109.
12. Khasanova, M. T. (2022). ANEMIA DURING PREGNANCY. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 1(4), 14-16.
13. Ходжаева, Н. Ж., Боймуродов, Х. Т., Абдиназаров, Х. Х., & Алиев, Б. Х. (2021). ВЛИЯНИЕ АБИОТИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ НА РАСПРОСТРАНЕННОСТЬ И ПЛОТНОСТЬ ВИДОВ СЕМЕЙСТВ UNIONIDAE, PISIDIDAE, EUGLESIDAE И CORVICULIDAE В ВЫСОКОГОРНЫХ РАЙОНАХ ПРИБРЕЖНОЙ ЗОНЫ КАШКАДАРЬИ. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 7(11), 28-33.
14. Боймуродов, Х. Т., Ходжаева, Н. Ж., Эгамкулов, А. Н., & Алиев, Б. Х. (2021). БИОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗНООБРАЗИЕ И РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЕ МОЛЛЮСКОВ СЕМЕЙСТВА UNIONIDAE И CORVICULIDAE В НИЗОВЬЯХ РЕКИ ЗАРАФШАН. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 7(11), 57-62.

15. Уразбаев, И. У., Хакбердиев, О. Э., & Ходжаева, Н. Ж. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ ЭРОЗИИ НА АГРОХИМИЧЕСКИЕ И МЕХАНИЧЕСКИЕ СВОЙСТВА БОГАРНЫХ ТИПИЧНЫХ И ТЕМНЫХ СЕРОЗЕМОВ. Актуальные проблемы современной науки, (6), 41-48.
16. Ходжаева, Н., Сайидханов, Т., Хамракулов, С., & Файзиева, Д. (2018). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ВОДНОГО ОБМЕНА ОЗИМОЙ ТВЁРДОЙ ПШЕНИЦЫ. In ADVANCED SCIENCE (pp. 129-132).
17. Nazarova, D. I. (2020). Jamol Kamolning Asru radifli g'azaliga yozgan muxammasi. Ilim ham ja'miyet. Ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal, (1), 93.
18. Nazarova D.I. Feelings of lyric heroes in Kamol Jamol"s work// Conference of Management of Islamic Education Leadership In The Era of Revolution.- 2020.- №6.- Pp. 1 - 3.
19. Ilhomovna, N. D. (2022). JAMOL KAMOLNING "SHAHRIBONU" DOSTONIDA VAZN XUSUSIYATLARINING TAHLILI. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(10), 254-264.
20. Ilhomovna, N. D. (2022). AXLOQIY-MA'RIFIY G'OYALAR TALQINLARI JAMOL KAMOL IJODIDA. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 102-108.
21. Ilhomovna, N. D. (2022). Mystical Content in the Poems of Jamal Kamal in Finger Weight. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 1(9), 208-215.
22. Nazarov, A. I. (2022). CONSEQUENCES OF SEIZURES AND EPILEPSY IN CHILDREN. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(02), 483-489.
23. Nazarov, A. I. (2022). ATROF-MUHITNING INSON SALOMATLIGIGA TA'SIRI. Scientific progress, 3(1), 881-885.
24. Ilhomovich, N. A. (2022). CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF COVID-19 DISEASE IN CHILDREN. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(9), 182-186.
25. Назаров, А. И. (2022). АУТИЗМ КАСАЛЛИКИНИ ЭРТА АНИҚЛАШДА ВА ДАВОЛАШДА ДАВО ЧОРАЛАРИНИ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШ ВА ДАВО САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ. Scientific progress, 3(1), 1143-1152.
26. Nazarov, A. (2021). CHALLENGES TO UZBEKISTAN'S SECURE AND STABLE POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION. Journal on International Social Science, 1(1), 26-31.
27. Nazarova, F., & Hudaikulova, N. (2019). Healthy generation-the basis of a healthy family. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(7), 69-73.

28. Nazarova, F. I. (2022). ABU ALI IBN SINONING SOG 'LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKILANIRISHI HAQIDA. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 1137-1142.
29. Ilkhomovna, N. F. (2022). Negative Impact of Seizures on Quality of Life. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 24, 120-122.
30. Ilhomovna, F. N. (2022). LATE SEIZURES AND CONSEQUENCES OF EPILEPSY IN YOUNG CHILDREN. *Conferencea*, 219-223.
31. Ilhomovna, F. N. (2022). RESPONSIBILITY OF PARENTS BEFORE THE OFFSPRING. *Conferencea*, 441-446.
32. Aminjonova, C. A. (2022). SOG'LOM ONA VA BOLA-BAXTLI KELAJAK ASOSI. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 874-880.
33. Akmalovna, A. C. (2022). Characteristics and Advantages of Soybean Benefits in Every way. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(8), 67-69.
34. Худойкулова, Н. И. (2018). Пути воспитания толерантности у молодежи. *Наука, техника и образование*, (11 (52)), 98-100.
35. Худайкулова, Н. И. (2022). ХИМИЧЕСКИЕ И ФИЗИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ И ИХ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ИММУННУЮ СИСТЕМУ ОРГАНИЗМА. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 891-895.
36. Худойкулова, Н. И. (2022). АНАЛИЗ И РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЕ ВРОЖДЕННЫХ АНОМАЛИЙ В БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 954-957.
37. KHUDOYKULOVA, N. (2022). CONGENITAL ANOMALIES, THEIR ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPMENT IN THE NAVOI REGION. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 46-
38. Аминжонова, Ч. А., & Мавлянова, Д. А. (2020). Методика преподавания предмета "биология" в системе высшего медицинского образования. In методологические и организационные подходы в психологии и педагогике (pp. 8-11).
39. Akmalovna, A. C., & Olimovna, A. G. (2020). Methodology and problems of teaching the subject "Biology" in medical universities and secondary educational schools. *Eurasian Medical Journal*, (2), 6-8.
40. Худайкулова, Н. И., & Жумаева, Ш. Б. (2020). О стимуляции иммунитета на гиалуронидазу-фактор патогенности паразитов. In *Университетская наука: взгляд в будущее* (pp. 106-108).